

The Ideal Child does not Play: Insights from Europe's Oldest Children's Book

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Introduction

Europe's oldest children's book was a bilingual easy reader designed to teach Greek to Roman schoolchildren.¹ Composed perhaps in the first century BC, it described a typical day in the life of a Roman schoolboy: getting ready for school, lessons, interactions with other children, lunch, etc. Although we no longer have this text exactly in its original form, it survives in multiple versions rewritten in subsequent centuries during the Roman empire.²

This children's book is a treasury of information on the daily lives of Roman children and the workings of Roman primary schools. We learn, for example, that schools had no set start times: each child got there when he or she happened to get there, and when one arrived, the first thing he or she did was to walk in and interrupt everyone by saying hello to the teacher and to all the other children. The teacher would stop what he was doing to return the greeting; this did not necessitate interrupting a lecture, because the teacher never did lecture to the class as a whole, but rather worked with each pupil individually in turn while the others studied independently. We also learn that in the morning Roman children first got dressed and then washed (this was possible because morning ablutions involved only the hands and face, with more extensive bathing taking place in the afternoon), and that they did not normally eat breakfast.

1. The Colloquia

This text is known by the rather cumbersome name of 'the schoolbook sections of the Colloquia of the Hermeneumata Pseudodositheana'. *Hermeneumata* is a Greek word

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- 1 I am grateful to Véronique Dasen for inviting me to the ERC conference « *Jeu et apprentissage* » (26-27.10.2017) for which this paper was originally composed, to Philomen Probert for advice and criticism, and to Christian Laes for allowing me to use his unpublished work (Laes, 2020).
 - 2 For a full edition and translation of this text, with commentary, see Dickey, 2012-2015; a translation can also be found in Dickey, 2017. For further information see e.g. Debut, 1984, 1987; Dionisotti, 1982; Ferri, 2008, 2011; Flammini, 2004; Goetz, 1892; Korhonen, 1996; Rochette, 2008; Tagliaferro, 2003.

designating a bilingual language-learning text in narrow columns; the ‘Hermeneumata Pseudodositheana’ are one group of such texts, a group formerly attributed to the fourth-century grammarian Dositheus but now known to predate him. They consist primarily of glossaries but also include sets of short dialogues and narratives known as ‘Colloquia’. These Colloquia are each composed of two parts, first a ‘schoolbook’ section describing the day of a child and then a ‘phrasebook’ section with dialogues covering the activities of an adult’s day.

The schoolbook sections were originally composed for Roman children learning Greek, a common activity in Roman schools. Schooling was far from universal in ancient Rome: only those whose parents could afford to pay fees had the chance to get an education, and some of those received only a strictly pre-professional training (for example studying to be a scribe). But children of the senatorial and equestrian ranks and from the wealthier plebeian families, that is children from the upper and middle classes, typically received a literary education, and these seem to have studied Greek from an early age. This practice applied to (at least some) girls as well as boys, for one of the Colloquia specifies in its preface that its intended audience was ‘all boys and girls’.³ We can learn more about the intended audience of the Colloquia schoolbooks from the children they describe, for the main character is a schoolboy with whom readers are clearly expected to identify. This boy tends to have an important father and several servants of his own: a paedagogue (a man who escorted the child to and from school), a personal slave boy to carry his schoolbooks, and sometimes a nurse.⁴

The phrasebook sections of the Colloquia have a completely different origin. They were designed for adult Greek speakers learning Latin and were composed (not in Rome but in the Greek-speaking areas of the Roman empire) considerably later than the schoolbooks, primarily in the second and third centuries AD. Their composers also rewrote the schoolbook sections to adapt them for adult Greek speakers, producing the composite versions that we have today. Only one version, the Colloquium Stephani, may have escaped such rewriting for adults. In the other versions it is not always possible to identify with certainty which elements of the schoolbooks come from the original Roman context and therefore describe the education of actual children, and which come from the Greek rewriting and therefore describe higher education. Nevertheless, it is highly likely that all references to concepts specifically associated with children (play, nurses, paedagogues, learning to read, etc.) come from the Roman original.

The passage below is an extract from one of these schoolbook sections, from the Colloquium Harleianum (sections 3a-5c). It shows a typical Roman boy arriving at school with his paedagogue and greeting the teacher – but then the boy asks the teacher to teach him to speak Latin. Roman children grew up speaking Latin and had to have that skill before starting school, and originally the one in this passage no doubt asked to learn Greek. But when the text started to be used by Greek speakers learning Latin, the request to learn Greek

3 Colloquium Celtis, section 1a.

4 In the Colloquia Monacensia–Einsidlensia (2e, 2h) the main character has a paedagogue, a nurse, and a slave boy. In the Colloquium Stephani (3a, 7b, 8a) he has a paedagogue and a slave boy. In the Colloquium Harleianum he has a nurse (8b), and his father is an important official (9a-e). In the Colloquium Celtis he has a paedagogue (15b, 28b, 46a), a nurse (3a), and a slave boy (6a, 22a, 44a); he is also stated to be well-born (9b). In the Colloquium Leidense–Stephani the main character gives orders to some kind of servant, though his/her identity is not specified (1e, 2a).

in this passage sounded absurd, and therefore it was changed to a request to learn Latin. The Greek and Latin columns are in their original ancient layout; they translate each other line for line,⁵ and the third column offers a modern English translation following a similar pattern, to the extent that English word order allows.

Ἀνάστα, παῖ· τί κάθησαι; ἄρον πάντα βιβλία τὰ Ῥωμαῖα, τὰς διφθέρας καὶ τὰς πινακίδας καὶ τὸν γλωσσοκόμον καὶ τὴν παράγραφον, τὸ μέλαν καὶ τοὺς καλάμους. ἀπέλθωμεν, ἀσπασώμεθα. Χαῖρε, κύριε διδάσκαλε, καλῶς σοι γένοιτο. ἀπὸ σήμερον φίλοπονείν θέλω. ἔρωτῶ σε οὖν, διδάξόν με Ῥωμαῖστί λαλεῖν. Διδάσκω σε, ἐάν με πρόσσχης. Ἰδοῦ, προσέχω.	Surge, puer; quid sedes? tolle omnes libros Latinos, membranas et pugillares et locellum et praeductal, atramentum et cannas. eamus, salutemus. Ave, domine praeceptor, bene tibi sit. ab hodie studere volo. rogo te ergo, doce me Latine loqui. Doceo te, si me attendas. Ecce, attendo.	‘Get up, boy; why are you sitting? Pick up all the Latin books, the parchment notebook and the tablets and the casket and the ruler, the ink and the pens. Let’s go, let’s greet [the teacher].’ ‘Hello, sir teacher! May it be well for you. From today to work hard I want. So please teach me to speak Latin.’ ‘I [shall] teach you, if you pay attention to me.’ ‘Look, I’m paying attention.’ ‘You have spoken well, as befits your good birth. Hand me, boy, the book-stand. So, quickly hand [me] the book, turn [to the right place], read aloud, open your mouth...’
Καλῶς εἶπας, ὡς πρέπει τῇ εὐγενείᾳ σου. ἐπίδος μοι, παῖ, τὸ ἀναλογεῖον. ταχέως οὖν ἐπίδος τὸ βιβλίον, ἀνεῖλησον, ἀνάγνωθι μετὰ φωνῆς, ἀνοιξόν τὸ στόμα...	Bene dixisti, ut decet ingenuitatem tuam. porrige mihi, puer, manuale. cito ergo porrige librum, revolve, lege cum voce, aperi os...	

5 For more information on the way this translation system worked, and its history, see Dickey, 2015.

2. Where is play?

Given this situation, one might expect the Colloquia to provide fascinating information on children's play. But they do not: play is mentioned only once in all the schoolbook sections, and that mention probably does not go back to the original text.⁶ It occurs in the Colloquium Harleianum, shortly after the extract just quoted (8a–9a). The teacher rebukes the child for truancy, leading the ancient reader to expect that the child will receive a whipping, the normal children's punishment for serious offences. But the child turns out to have an excellent excuse, enabling him to give the teacher a crushing put-down: his father, who is clearly far more important than the teacher will ever be, took him to town on important business. In this passage the Greek and the Latin sometimes say slightly different things, which are both translated in the English, separated with a slash.

Ἐχθές	Heri	'Yesterday
ἤρησας	cessabas	you slacked off
καὶ δειλῆς	et meridie	and in the afternoon / at midday
εἰς τὴν οἰκίαν	in domum	at home
(ἔπαιζες)	(ludebas)	(you were playing)
οὐκ ἦς.	non eras.	you were not.
ἔγώ σε	ego te	I looked for you
ἔζήτησα	quaesivi	
καὶ ἤκουσα πάντα	et audivi omnia	and I heard everything
παρὰ τοῦ τροφῆος σου,	ab alumno tuo,	from your nurse / nursling,
ἄπερ ἐποίησας.	quae fecisti.	what you did.'
Ψεύδεται	Mentitur	'He's lying,
ὁ σοὶ εἰπὼν,	qui tibi dixit,	the person who spoke to you,
ἦγεν γάρ με	duxit enim me	for my father took me
ὁ πατήρ μου	pater meus	
εἰς τὸ πραιτώριον	in praetorium	to the praetorium
μεθ' ἑαυτοῦ.	secum.	with him.'

In this passage the word *ἔπαιζες/ludebas*, "you were playing", is incompatible with *οὐκ ἦς/non eras*, "you were not" in the next line: the two are evidently alternatives, since a child can be playing at home or not be at home, but not both.⁷ The provision of alternatives is not uncommon in the Colloquia, because language learners need the ability to say a range of different things; sometimes there are two, as here, and sometimes more. In some passages all the alternatives could be original, and in others it is probable that one is original and the other(s) a more recent addition to the text. This passage falls into the latter category, for

6 There are also some mentions of play in the phrasebook sections, for example playing ball at the baths (Colloquia Monacensia–Einsidlensia, 10h), but these cannot be proved to refer to children's play. The characters in the phrasebook sections all appear to be adults when their ages can be determined; one can interpret the bathing scenes as involving children as well as adults (and I have done so, e.g. Dickey, 2017, p. 88), but there is no real proof that any children are involved; see Dickey, 2012-15, vol. 1, p. 172.

7 Other possibilities, such as playing somewhere other than home, may be theoretically possible, but they are not grammatically feasible here: the line *εἰς τὴν οἰκίαν/in domum* 'at home' has to be taken with each verb.

in addition to the medieval manuscript from which the text of the *Colloquium Harleianum* primarily comes, there is a papyrus fragment of this passage. Although the text of the papyrus is not the direct ancestor of the text in the manuscript, it is about 500 years earlier and therefore a far better witness to the wording of the original.⁸ It reads *in domum non eras*, “you were not at home” (the Greek is lost), with no trace of *ludebas*, “you were playing”.

3. Play as the antithesis of learning

Originally, therefore, the Roman children’s book probably contained no mention of play at all. Why was that, and why did a later adaptor choose to add a mention just here? The answers to both questions seem to lie in a belief that children’s play was antithetical to their learning: children could only learn if they studied, and they could not study while playing.⁹ As children needed to learn in order to have successful adult lives, loving parents and responsible teachers had to punish them for playing, making play a stereotypical sin of children. Such a perspective is visible in St Augustine’s comments about the beatings he endured during his sinful childhood:

non enim deerat, domine, memoria vel ingenium, quae nos habere voluisti pro illa aetate satis, sed delectabat ludere et vindicabatur in nos ab eis qui talia utique agebant. sed maiorum nugae negotia vocantur, puerorum autem talia cum sint, puniuntur a maioribus, et nemo miseratur pueros vel illos vel utrosque. nisi vero approbat quisquam bonus rerum arbiter vapulasse me, quia ludebam pila puer et eo ludo impediabar quominus celeriter discerem litteras, quibus maior deformius luderem. aut aliud faciebat idem ipse a quo vapulabam, qui si in aliqua quaestiuicula a conductore suo victus esset, magis bile atque invidia torqueretur quam ego, cum in certamine pilae a conclusore meo superabar?

“For, Lord, we did not lack memory and talent, which you wanted us to have enough of for that age, but we loved to play, and they punished that in us, they who were actually doing something similar. For the sillinesses of grown-ups are called business, but when boys are silly, they are punished by the grown-ups, and no-one pities either the boys or the grown-ups. Unless perhaps some good judge of affairs might think it was right for me to be beaten, because being a boy I used to play ball and by that playing was hindered from quickly learning my letters, by means of which when grown I would play worse games? Or was he by whom I was beaten doing anything different, since if he was defeated by a fellow-teacher in any little question, he was tortured with greater bile and envy than I was when defeated by my playmate in a game of ball?”¹⁰

8 For further information on the papyrus and its relationship to the manuscript, see Dickey and Ferri, 2012, and Dickey, 2012-2015, vol. 2, p. 5-7, 56-59). The date at which the reference to play was added cannot be determined, but it must have been during antiquity, not during the Carolingian period from which the manuscript comes. All extant medieval manuscripts of the *Colloquia* come from places where copyists did not know enough Greek to add words that matched in Greek and Latin, and therefore they very rarely added lines to the *Colloquia*.

9 For a different cultural evaluation of play in children’s life, see N. Mathieu, V. Dasen in this volume.

10 *Confessions*, 1.9 (transl. E. Dickey). On Augustine’s considerations about play, see in this volume A.-I. Bouton-Touboulic.

The schoolbook sections of the Colloquia, like many a children's book from later centuries, depict an idealized schoolboy. He is polite, studious, intelligent, and scrupulously clean and tidy. Consider these passages from the different versions:

ἔγραψα οὖν
ἐμὸν ὄνομα·
καὶ οὕτως ἐστάθην,
ἕως οἱ προάγοντες
ἀπέδωκαν,
καὶ προσέσχον
ὑποκρίσεις
καθηγητοῦ
καὶ συμμαθητοῦ.
καὶ γὰρ ἐκείθεν
προκόπτομεν,
προσέχοντες ἄλλοις,
εἴ τι αὐτοῖς
δεικνύοιτο.

scripsi ergo
meum nomen;
et ita steti,
donec antecedentes
reddiderunt,
et attendi
pronuntiationes
praeceptoris,
et condiscipuli.
etenim inde
proficimus,
attendentes aliis,
siquid ipsi
monentur.

[Child narrator:] 'So I wrote
my name;
and I stood like that
until those ahead of me
produced [their work],
and I paid attention to
the pronunciations
of the teacher,
and of [my] fellow student.
For it is from this
that we progress,
[from] paying attention to others,
if something is demonstrated to them / if
they are advised of something.'

(Colloquium Stephani 11a–d)

Πράξον οὖν
ἐπιμελῶς,
ἵνα ἐτοιμὸς ᾖς.
Ἐτοιμὸς εἰμι·
ἦψα γὰρ
τὸν λύχνον
καὶ νύκτωρ
ἐμελέτησα.
Καλῶς ἐποίησας·
ἄρτι σε ἐπαινῶ.

Age ergo
diligenter,
ut paratus sis.
Paratus sum;
incendi enim
lucernam
et nocte
meditatus sum.
Bene fecisti;
modo te laudo.

[Teacher:] 'So behave
carefully,
so that you will be ready.'
[Child:] 'I am ready;
for I lit
the lamp
and at night
I studied.'
[Teacher:] 'You have done well;
now I praise you.'

(Colloquium Harleianum 6d–f)

Καθηγητά, χαῖρε.
ἐπειδὴ θέλω
καὶ λίαν ἐπιθυμῶ
λαλεῖν Ἑλληνιστὶ
καὶ Ῥωμαϊστὶ,
ἔρωτώ σε, ἐπιστάτα,
δίδαξόν με.
Ἐγὼ ποιήσω,
ἐάν μοι πρόσχημις.
Προσέχω σοι
ἐπιμελῶς.

Praeceptor, ave.
quoniam volo
et valde cupio
loqui Graece
et Latine,
rogo te, magister,
doce me.
Ego faciam,
si me attendas.
Attendo te
diligenter.

[Child:] 'Teacher, hello!
Since I want
and exceedingly desire
to speak in Greek
and in Latin,
please, teacher,
teach me.'
[Teacher:] 'I shall do [that],
if you pay attention to me.'
[Child:] 'I am paying attention to you
carefully.'

(Colloquium Montepessulanum 2a–b)

<p>ἐνθεν ὕστερον προέρχομαι ἐκ τοῦ οἴκου εἰς δημόσιον (εἰς ἀκροατήριον, εἰς γέφυραν, εἰς κώμην, εἰς ἀγοράν), σὺν τῷ ἐμῷ παιδίῳ καμπροφύρῳ (ἢ παιδαγωγῷ ἢ συμμαθητῇ). εἴ τις γνωστός ἢ φίλος συνήντησέν μοι, ἀσπάζομαι αὐτὸν τῷ αὐτοῦ ὀνόματι. ἀντασπάζεται με τῷ ἐμῷ ὀνόματι.</p>	<p>hinc postea procedo de domo in publicum (in auditorium, in pontem, in vicum, in forum), cum meo puero capsario (aut paedagogo aut condiscipulo). si quis notus aut amicus occurrit mihi, saluto eum nomine suo. resalutat me nomine meo.</p>	<p>[Child narrator:] From there afterwards I proceed from home outside (to the lecture hall, to the bridge, to the village, to the forum), with my boy who carries my case of books (or my paedagogue or my fellow student). If any acquaintance or friend met me, I greet him with his name. He in return greets me with my name.'</p>
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(Colloquium Celtis 15a–16b)

For writers who considered play to be inherently naughty, such a child could not without contradiction be depicted playing, any more than he could be depicted being rude to his teacher, beating up other children, or failing to learn his lessons.

Why, then, was the single reference to play added? Probably because in the passage where it occurs, the ideal child is the victim of a false accusation: someone has alleged that he did something he should not have done. Being an ideal child, he responds to that accusation by vindicating himself decisively and convincing the teacher that he was in fact engaged in serious business. Originally, the accusation itself was somewhat strange: it alleged that the child had not been at home in the afternoon (or at midday). But why should he have been at home? Some Roman children were home educated rather than attending school, but this boy can hardly have been among them, for the first passage quoted above shows him collecting his books, going off to school, and greeting the teacher. Indeed all the versions of the Colloquia schoolbooks depict actual schools rather than home education, making it evident that the setting in a school is one of the work's original features. Probably the author of the original version of the false-accusation passage was envisioning some context in which censoring a child for not being at home made sense, but either he neglected to make that context clear to readers or the original clarification later disappeared. The passage was then left as it appears in the papyrus, with the child being blamed for something that was not obviously naughty. At some point a teacher using this text decided to improve this situation by adding an alternative that made more sense as an accusation of naughtiness. The fact that what he chose to add was an accusation that the child had been playing is additional confirmation of the existence of a mindset in which play was inherently naughty.

4. How widespread was that view?

But could Romans really have such a wholly negative view of play? Recently Christian Laes has collected evidence for the presence of play in ancient schools; there is some such evidence from the Roman period, even if it is far from extensive.¹¹ For example, the first-century teacher Quintilian advocated giving very young children ivory letters as playthings to stimulate them to learn the alphabet¹² and stated that he was not opposed to play in moderation for older children.¹³ So if other Romans saw play as inherently naughty, there must have been some differences of opinion. Such diversity is unsurprising, since Roman culture was both geographically and chronologically diverse, and Romans were as capable of independent thought as anyone else. Can we establish whether there was a majority view, and if so, what it was?

One potential source of information is the word for ‘play’ itself, *ludus*. From an early period *ludus* meant both ‘play’ and ‘school’,¹⁴ and that linguistic connection might in theory suggest a deeper relationship, perhaps indicating a positive view of play as an educational force. But in fact it did not, for numerous Roman grammarians considered the two meanings of *ludus* to be opposites. Quintilian, complaining about preposterous etymologies proposed by grammarians, remarked:

etiamne a contrariis aliqua sinemus trahi, ut ‘lucus’ quia umbra opacus parum luceat, et ‘ludus’ quia sit longissime a lusu, et ‘Ditis’ quia minime dives?

“But should we also admit that some words are derived from their opposites, such as “grove” (*lucus*) because being dark with shade it has very little light (*luceat*), and “school” (*ludus*) because it is very far from play (*lusu*), and “Pluto” (*Ditis*) because he is not at all rich (*dives*)?”¹⁵

A century later Sextus Pompeius Festus claimed:

ludi appellantur, in quibus minime luditur, ne tristi aliquo nomine fug<iant pueri suo fungi mu>nerē

“The places in which there is the least play (*luditur*) are called schools (*ludi*) lest the children flee from their task because of an alarming name.”¹⁶

Both these comments reflected the ideas of earlier grammarians; Festus was summarizing a (now lost) work entitled *De verborum significatu*, *On the meaning of words*, composed at the beginning of the first century AD by M. Verrius Flaccus, and Quintilian’s source may have been Aelius Stilo, who lived around 100 BC.¹⁷ The idea that the two meanings of *ludus*

11 Laes, 2020.

12 Quint. *Inst.* 1.1.26.

13 Quint. *Inst.* 1.3.10-12.

14 See e.g. Glare, 1968-1982, s.v. *ludus*. The ‘play’ meaning seems to be older and may have given rise to the ‘school’ meaning via military training exercises: see Bonner, 1977, p. 57, and Laes, 2020, section 2. Later *ludus* ‘school’ was largely supplanted by *schola* (from Greek σχολή, which had a similar double meaning).

15 Quint. *Inst.* 1.6.34 (transl. E. Dickey).

16 Festus, *fragmenta e cod. Farn. L.XIX* = Lindsay, 1913, p. 470; cf. *Thesaurus Linguae Latinae*, s.v. *ludus* p. 1792.26-31.

17 See Funaioli, 1907, p. 72 (n° 59).

were opposed seems therefore to have been well embedded in Roman linguistic thought by the time of the early empire.¹⁸

This type of linguistic argument would not have worked if many Romans had thought that play could be a part of education rather than its opposite. Had that been the case, the derivations above would have seemed clearly wrong and would not have been worth repeating. Therefore, even if there was a range of opinions about play, St Augustine's view that it was inherently naughty was probably more widespread than Quintilian's more nuanced approach.¹⁹ The scarcity of mentions of play in the schoolbook sections of the *Colloquia* therefore can perhaps be explained by a common Roman view of playing as something that schoolchildren ought ideally not to do.

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¹⁸ See further Laes, 2020, section 2.

¹⁹ Quintilian seems to have been unusually enlightened for a Roman teacher; he disapproved of beating children, despite acknowledging that it was usual to do so; cf. *Inst.* 1.3.13–17.

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